

38 **1 Introduction**

39 Warehousing and support activities for transportation is a subsector of the transport and
40 storage services business sector, with a significant impact on the global economy. For
41 instance, in the Europe Union, this sector generated €487.1 billion of value added in 2018,
42 the fifth greater in EU's economy, representing 7.4% of the wealth generated in the non-
43 financial business economy (EuroStat). Specifically, the warehousing subsector employed
44 nearly 2.5 million persons, most of them working in Germany, France, Italy and Spain. In
45 other words, warehouses are civil engineering structures that play an important role in the
46 society, providing a safe place for the goods to be stored before their large distribution to
47 the public (Gu et al. 2007). At the same time, they are concentrated points of failure in an
48 otherwise widely distributed logistics system.

49 In order to provide flexibility in the handling process and to accommodate a large variety
50 of stored goods, warehouses come in all kinds of structural configurations (Tilburgs 2013).
51 Typically, one considers a warehouse as a combination of an external shell and a series of
52 racks or shelves that support the merchandise; however, this is not always the case (Vujanac
53 et al. 2017). Integrated solutions are proliferating, where the racks also support the cladding
54 and facade in the so-called Rack-Supported Warehouses (RSWs). Innovation is not limited
55 in the structural configuration but also extends to the handling process, providing automated
56 management systems for storage and retrieval using integrated artificial intelligence and
57 robotics. Considering also the nature of the stockpiled wares, there is a virtually "infinite"
58 number of warehouse configurations, each characterized by specific attributes such as
59 dimensions, used material, automation etc.

60 Seismic-motion events on industrial areas over the past years have showed the vulnerability
61 of many warehouses to lateral loads (Bournas et al. 2014). Storage racks, whether they
62 support the whole building or not (i.e. indoor racks), are made of slender members that carry
63 high live-loads; this renders them susceptible to various types of member buckling and
64 global geometric non-linearities (i.e. P- Δ effects).

65 During the Christchurch earthquake series of 2010 and 2011 (Clifton et al. 2011), several
66 indoor storage racks collapsed (Figure 1a), despite the fact that the owners of the warehouses
67 took measures or retrofitted the racks between the two events. In the Emilia-Romagna
68 earthquake in 2012 it was estimated that 633,700 wheels of Parmigiano Reggiano and Grana
69 Padano cheese were damaged by falling off factory shelves where they were maturing
70 (Franco et al. 2015), with the cost of the damage estimated at €150 million (Figure 1b).
71 Partial or even global collapses of RSWs were also reported during the Emilia-Romagna
72 earthquake in 2012 (Figure 2). It is worth mentioning that currently no official provisions
73 exist for the design of RSWs; designers are obliged to treat them as standard racking
74 systems, adopting low-ductility concepts and disregarding capacity-design rules. There is
75 also a large percentage of racks that are not even designed for seismic loads, despite being
76 installed in earthquake-prone areas. However, considering the economic impact that a
77 collapse of a warehouse has on the society, it is questionable whether low-cost outweighs
78 resilience.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Failure of indoor racking structures during seismic motions, showing (a): partial collapse of an adjustable steel rack during the Christchurch earthquake of 2011 (Clifton et al. 2011) and (b): collapse of cantilever-like racks used for Parmigiano Reggiano cheese wheels in a warehouse in Emilia Romagna (Franco et al. 2015).

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Figure 2: Collapse of Ceramic Storage warehouse in Sant' Agostino due to 2012 Emilia-Romagna earthquake, Italy (Kanyilmaz et al. 2016).

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81 The large variation of characteristics among different racking systems, not unlike the
82 differences among types of conventional buildings, means that lumping all types into a
83 single "warehouse class" can become a gross oversimplification. Instead, by defining a
84 uniform taxonomy, there are distinct advantages to be had: (a) by facilitating the comparison
85 of results between different studies, (b) selecting vulnerability/fragility functions for
86 portfolio or regional risk/loss assessment studies, and (c) collecting usable damage/loss data
87 in post-earthquake surveys. While manufacturers and designers of steel racks do employ a
88 fairly wide categorization of structural systems, they also tend to focus on functionality,

89 usability and performance from a logistics point of view; such attributes are not necessarily
90 important for guiding vulnerability assessment. Similarly, rack design codes may employ
91 some elements of classification (e.g. EN 16681 2016), yet these are not comprehensive
92 enough to fit the purposes of a full taxonomy for vulnerability assessment. Instead, we
93 propose distilling current industrial classifications to delineate a collapsible, flexible and
94 extensible set of classes that can encode the salient structural characteristics of existing,
95 contemporary and upcoming racking systems, akin to literature taxonomies for typical
96 buildings, e.g., by the Global Earthquake Model (GEM) (Brzev et al. 2013) or the EERI and
97 IAEE World Housing Encyclopedia (Brzev and Greene 2004). In turn we offer perspective
98 regarding the expected behavior, as well as a common glossary to support efficient
99 identification and assessment by risk analysts.

100

101 **2 Morphology of Racking Systems**

102 Steel racking systems commonly comprise cold-formed members that can be easily
103 assembled and adjusted to serve the continuously changing needs of a warehouse. While
104 some members can be made of hot-rolled steel, such as some angle-L sections in the bracing
105 system, a rack completely made of hot-rolled sections is considered not to be economically
106 viable, due to the heavy connections needed with respect to the cold-formed solutions.
107 Typically, in a racking system one defines two primary directions, the down-aisle direction
108 which is used by the forklift trucks in order to deposit and withdraw the goods and,
109 perpendicularly, the cross-aisle (EN 15512).

110 Figure 3 illustrates the primary components of the most common rack configuration, the
111 Adjustable Pallet Racking system (APR system, also referred to as “selective” system).
112 Individual or boxed items are combined into single “units”, so-called unit loads, that can be
113 moved easily with a pallet jack or forklift truck. They typically consist of corrugated
114 fiberboard boxes stacked on a pallet or slip sheet and stabilized with stretch wrap. Each unit
115 load is characterized by a Stock Keeping Unit (SKU), a unique identifier that is used to
116 classify the stored goods inside a warehouse. Unit loads of the same SKU are considered
117 identical and thus, interchangeable. In APR systems, the pallets are accommodated by the
118 pallet beams that are hooked (Figure 4b) or bolted to the uprights, creating a Moment
119 Resisting Frame (MRF) in the down-aisle direction (Bernuzzi and Simoncelli 2016b). In the
120 cross-aisle direction, the uprights are connected by a bracing system (Figure 4a) with a D,
121 Z, K or X bracing pattern (EN 15512), defining the so-called upright frames (Figure 3).
122 Racking systems are typically fixed on a concrete ground slab using a base plate and post-
123 installed anchors (Figure 4b), however there are some exceptional cases where the racks are
124 installed on asphalt, tiles or even suspended floors.

125 Other traditional types of storage racks are the drive-in and the drive-through systems.
126 Drive-in racks allow a lift truck to enter the rack from one side to pick up or lay down
127 pallets, which are placed on a continuous rail beam (Figure 5). From a logistics point of
128 view, drive-in racks are efficient when one has a large number of similar items that can be
129 stored in a single “input/output” pallet position and accessed via the Last-In, First-Out
130 method. Access is provided through a single aisle in the front of the rack. The fact that the

131 forklifts need to drive into the racks leads to the absence of pallet beams, with the exception
132 of the “portal” beams at the highest level of the rack. As a result, drive-in racks cannot rely
133 on this extremely weak MRF to resist the lateral loads and a bracing system is always
134 mandatory. When the vertical bracing is placed eccentrically at the one end of the rack, so
135 called spine bracing, horizontal braces are also placed in order to provide in-plane stiffness
136 diaphragm at the top level (Cheng and Wu 2016), as shown in Figure 5. On the other hand,
137 some manufacturers prefer to sacrifice one bay and install a concentric vertical bracing
138 system, the so-called bracing towers, a lateral force resisting system that is used also in other
139 racking systems. Finally, the drive-through system is identical to the drive-in from a
140 structural point of view; the only difference is that drive-through racks allow the lift truck
141 to enter through both ends of the system allowing for a First-In, First-Out storage option,
142 but requiring aisles on both the front and the back of the rack.

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Figure 3: Primary structural components of an Adjustable Pallet Racking (APR) system and definition of the down- and cross-aisle directions (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.a.).

144

145 A more modern approach to the Last-In, First-Out method, is the pallet shuttle racking
146 system (Huang et al. 2012). Lately, these systems are preferred over the traditional drive-
147 in, as they allow working on each load level individually, while in the drive-in each bay
148 must have items with the same SKU. The pallet shuttle racks are characterized by a multi-
149 depth structure, where the unit loads are stored in long storage tunnels, serviced by
150 mechanical shuttles which are positioned by traditional forklift trucks or cranes (Figure 6).
151 As the shuttles are moving along the cross-aisle direction, like the lift trucks do in the drive-
152 in system, rail beams are also mandatory in this system, with the difference that they are not
153 connected directly to the uprights but on pallet beams. As the pallet beams now need only
154 to accommodate one pallet per bay, their cross-sections are lighter with respect to those of

155 the APR system and thus the formed MRF is somewhat flexible. Thus, in seismic areas
156 bracing towers are frequently placed at the one or both ends of the racking system.
157

Figure 4: Component connections of an APR system showing: (a) a diagonal-to-upright bolted connection and (b) a beam-to-column hooked connection and an upright-to-floor connection (photos courtesy of SACMA S.p.a.).

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Figure 5: Primary structural components of a drive-in steel racking system. In drive-in racks, the forklifts enter inside the rack in order to deposit and withdraw the pallets (photo courtesy of Nedcon B.V.).

159

160 The state of the art in storage technology are the Automated Rack Supported Warehouses
161 (ARSWs), racking systems that employ automated storage procedures, while supporting
162 both the stored pallets and the external cladding shell (Tsarpalis et al. 2021). ARSWs
163 maximize the exploitation of the available footprint by achieving far greater heights than
164 the traditional systems (e.g. 30 meters tall). This is achieved by connecting the upright
165 frames by a roof truss, avoiding the construction of an independent shell-supporting
166 structure. Two main types can be distinguished based on their configuration and handling
167 system, namely the automated double-depth cranes (Figure 7) and the automated multi-
168 depth shuttles (Figure 8). Double-depth cranes belong to direct-access systems and provide
169 easy accessibility to the pallets, stored with a maximum number of two units for each row
170 in the cross-aisle direction, but decrease the use of the available footprint of the warehouse
171 by needing more aisles. On the other hand, multi-depth shuttles are more compact systems
172 that maximize the storage density, while losing accessibility to the pallets that are stored in
173 long storage tunnels serviced by mechanized shuttles running on rails, which renders them
174 more suitable for handling a reduced number of SKUs.

175

Figure 6: Configuration of a multi-depth pallet shuttle racking system. Pallets are stored in long storage tunnels serviced by mechanized shuttles running on rails (photo courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

176

Figure 7: Example of a double-depth ARSW in the construction stage (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.a.).

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Figure 8: Example of a multi-depth ARSW in the construction stage (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.a.).

178

179 Cantilever racks are used to easily store long products that typical pallet rack openings
180 cannot handle, like steel profiles, steel or aluminum sheets, lumber, plywood, pipes etc.
181 They employ a single upright that is perforated along the height to accommodate small
182 cantilever beams, used to store the linear wares (Figure 9). The uprights are not made of
183 open sections like in the other racking systems, but of rectangular hollow sections as no
184 upright frame is formed in the cross-aisle direction. Instead, cross-aisle stability of the single
185 upright acting as a cantilever is achieved solely by the moment-connection to a horizontal

186 beam fixed to the foundation floor (FEM 10.2.09 2013). On the down-aisle direction, a light
187 bracing system is used, as the small horizontal elements that connect the uprights offer
188 negligible moment-framing action.

Figure 9: Example of a heavy-duty cantilever rack (photo courtesy of Modulblok).

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190 A popular solution for domestic applications, libraries and superstores/markets open to the
191 public is the light-duty hand-loaded shelving rack (Figure 10). It is used to store light-weight
192 products on small boxes, trays or containers using hand-picking methods. The shelves that
193 carry the unit-loads can be directly connected to the uprights by means of bolts and clips, or
194 supported on beams (Bernuzzi et al. 2016a). Lateral stability in the down-aisle direction is
195 provided by the semi-rigid moment connection between the beam-like edges of the shelf
196 sheeting or by actual beams supporting said sheeting, if they are present. In the cross-aisle
197 direction, one may employ (i) a bracing system forming lighter versions of the APR upright
198 frames, (ii) a light moment-frame based on beam-like lacing members (Figure 10 left), or
199 (iii) a combination of the two (Figure 10 right). Despite being low-rise structures carrying
200 light goods, an abrupt collapse of a shelving rack might lead to loss of human life, apart
201 from the economic impact due to damage on the stored wares.

202

Figure 10: Typical shelving rack and key components (adopted from Bernuzzi et al. 2016a).

203

204 Finally, two niche rack typologies are the mobile and gravity flow racking systems. A
 205 mobile system comprises a series of independent APR or cantilever racks, without static
 206 aisles to separate them; instead, they are motorized and, guided by rails, they may move
 207 along the cross-aisle direction to open up an aisle where needed, (Figure 11). Thus, mobile
 208 systems maximize the exploitation of the available footprint as the individual racks move to
 209 create the only required aisle for withdrawal and retrieval. Gravity flow racking systems are
 210 structurally similar to the well-known APRs but employ a different logistic workflow: By
 211 sliding units along inclined rails (or surfaces), they take advantage of gravity to load,
 212 organize and retrieve. From a logistics point of view, gravity flow racks can be broken down
 213 to three sub-categories: The push-back (Figure 12), pallet-flow and carton-flow racking
 214 system.

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Figure 11: Example of a mobile racking system (photo courtesy of Modulblok).

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217

Figure 12: Example of a push-back gravity flow racking system (photo courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

218

219 **3 Seismic behavior and design of racks**

220 The design of steel racking systems is always accompanied by experimental tests, as they
221 comprise thin-walled perforated members with semi-rigid connections whose actual
222 strength and stiffness cannot be accurately calculated by analysis. The compression strength
223 of the uprights is negatively influenced by the presence of holes and thus, local buckling of
224 the section is typically the dominant failure mode (Vayas et al. 2019). However, depending
225 on the thickness-to-braced-length ratio, distortional buckling may also prevail, which can
226 be identified either by means of experimental tests on full-scale upright frames or by
227 numerical analyses (Elias et al. 2018, Miranda et al. 2018). In the cross-aisle direction, the
228 shear stiffness of the upright frame is degraded by the axial deformation of the braces and
229 their ends, as well as the slipping and bending of the bolts (Talebian et al. 2018). Structural
230 engineers take this phenomenon into account in a conventional beam element model by
231 applying a reduction, of the order of 95%, to the brace cross-sectional area according to
232 shear tests on individual upright frames. Experimental calibration is also needed for the
233 beam-to-column rack joints in order to determine the moment-rotation curve of the
234 connection, whose hysteretic response is characterized by slippage, pinching and stiffness-
235 degrading behavior (Bernuzzi and Simoncelli 2016b).

236 While the aforementioned local component tests are applicable to all types of racking
237 systems, at the system level the focus of existing literature has been on the APR systems
238 and for a good reason, as they comprise the most frequently used rack typology. Moreover,
239 the logic of upright frames in the cross-aisle direction and MRFs in the down-aisle direction
240 is also adopted in other systems, like the double- and multi-depth ARSWs. As a result,
241 design codes are available almost solely for the adjustable racks and it is the designer's

242 responsibility to extend them to other systems. For instance, in USA, APRs are presently
243 designed according to the Rack Manufacturer Institute (RMI) specification (2012), in
244 Europe per EN 15512 (2009), while in Australia the AS 4084 (2012) standard is used.

245 Analysis and design become even more complicated when a storage rack is used in seismic
246 areas where the structures have to withstand additional horizontal seismic forces. In most
247 cases, the codes applicable to conventional buildings were employed, e.g., EN 1998-1
248 (2004) in Europe. Still, these are typically not sufficient to cover the seismic design of
249 racking systems, thus additional provisions emerged. For example, the Federation
250 Européenne De La Manutention (FEM) guideline 10.2.08 (2011) extended the provisions
251 of Eurocode 8 with the introduction of additional elements specifically applicable to racks
252 and governed the seismic design of racking systems in Europe from 2008 to 2016, until the
253 introduction of EN 16681 (2016), which is now the de facto European seismic code for
254 racking systems. In USA, RMI (2012) covers both seismic and non-seismic aspects.

255 Research done so far has demonstrated that typical APR systems offer limited ductility,
256 which is reflected in the design codes by the adoption of low behavior (or strength reduction)
257 factors (e.g. 1.5 and 2.0 in the cross- and the down-aisle direction, respectively (EN 16681
258 2016). In the cross-aisle direction, the horizontal seismic loads are balanced by a set of axial
259 forces acting on the uprights, which are optimized to the maximum, leading to buckling
260 failure modes before the bracing system enters the nonlinear range. Even if the uprights
261 were capacity designed, special connection detailing would be mandatory for the braces in
262 order to prevent bolt or bearing failure, a capacity check adopted in conventional steel
263 buildings but seldomly in racks.

264 In the down-aisle direction, the flexible MRF relies on the hysteretic behavior of the hooked
265 beam-to-column joint to absorb plastic deformations (or dissipate energy in Eurocode
266 parlance). Yin L. et al. (2016) conducted several monotonic and cyclic loading tests on
267 beam-to-column connections and found that by introducing additional bolts and welds, the
268 hysteretic response of the joint can be improved in terms of stiffness degradation and
269 deformability. However, in high seismicity areas, the weak MRF is not always capable of
270 resisting the increased horizontal forces and the contribution of the second-order effects
271 becomes crucial. To alleviate this issue, designers typically install a vertical bracing system
272 (Figure 13), also called spine bracing, that enhances the stiffness of the structure but not the
273 ductility as the design codes do not mandate capacity design. Still, full-scale pushover tests
274 (Castiglioni et al. 2014, Kanyilmaz et al. 2016) demonstrated that higher behavior factors
275 can be achieved on braced racks by guaranteeing sufficient overstrength for the bracing
276 connections to avoid a sudden brittle failure, such as bolt shear and bolt bending failures
277 before brace yielding.

278

Figure 13: Spine bracing layout (adopted from FEM 10.2.08 2011).

279

280 On the other hand, the design of drive-in racks is not well covered or documented in the
 281 literature. Gilbert et al. (2012, 2014) presented the structural behavior of drive-in racks
 282 under static loading, both in terms of experimental and analytical results. It was shown that
 283 the friction between pallet bases and rail beams provides additional horizontal bracing
 284 restraints on the system, however this contribution is relatively low in the overall design of
 285 the rack. Still, the work done focused on static loading conditions. A recent work by
 286 Shaheen and Rasmussen (2019) shed some light to the dynamic response of the drive-in
 287 racks along the cross-aisle direction by means of shaking table tests, concluding that the
 288 upright-to-diagonal connections experience severe local damage that led to brittle type of
 289 failures. For practical applications, the European Racking Federation design guideline FEM
 290 10.2.07 (2012), which is perhaps the only widely available guideline specialized to drive-in
 291 racks, does not offer a seismic design procedure. If one extrapolates from APR system
 292 guidelines, a behavior factor equal to 2.0 might seem appropriate in down-aisle direction
 293 but it is unclear whether this assumption is safe given that relevant research is lacking and
 294 there is higher flexibility in drive-in systems relative to APRs that may lead to earlier-than-
 295 expected failures.

296 Finally, there are racking systems whose structural behavior is yet to be examined in detail,
 297 as research has not yet caught up to the rapid developments in racking technology. Some of
 298 these systems have many similarities with the well-known adjustable racks, with only some
 299 particular aspects remaining as a gray area. For instance, the recently-introduced pallet
 300 shuttle system (Figure 6) resembles an APR but it also comprises horizontal grids of pallet
 301 and rail beams at each load level that can provide some beneficial diaphragm stiffness,
 302 which may or may not be accounted for in design, and may or may not act as additional
 303 overstrength in assessment. On the other hand, there are many widely-used and non-APR-

304 like systems for which little experimental and analytical research is available, and design
305 guides are either totally absent, or they only exist for non-seismic conditions (e.g. FEM
306 10.2.09 (2013) and FEM 10.2.06 (2012) for the cantilever (Figure 9) and shelving racks
307 (Figure 10), respectively). Another example are the massive ARSWs (Figure 7 and Figure
308 8); such systems cannot always be treated as “very tall” APRs, among other reasons due to
309 their high importance, the effect of pallet load distribution and automated pallet sorting
310 algorithms, the high degree of optimization to minimize costs, and the subsequent razor-
311 thin overstrength margins.

312

313 **4 Proposed taxonomy**

314 The sole purpose of a rack taxonomy is to describe and classify racks in a uniform manner
315 as a key step towards assessing their risk to various hazards, such as seismic or extreme
316 wind phenomena. While many taxonomies exist worldwide, such as the GEM (Brzev et al.
317 2013), EERI and IAEE World Housing Encyclopedia (Brzev and Greene 2004), PAGER-
318 STR (Jaiswal and Wald 2008, USGS & WHE 2008) and HAZUS (FEMA 2003) taxonomy,
319 they mainly target conventional buildings. For example, the Building Taxonomy adopted
320 by the Global Earthquake Model (GEM) Foundation comprises eight basic “Attributes” (or
321 classes per other taxonomic systems) required to broadly characterize any building: (i)
322 material of the lateral load resisting system, (ii) lateral load-resisting system (iii) roof, (iv)
323 floor, (v) height, (vi) date of construction, (vii) structural irregularity, and (viii) occupancy.
324 Each “Attribute” may be further broken down to several “Attribute Levels” delineating, e.g.,
325 the different available materials or types of lateral load-resisting systems, and then further
326 discretized to several “Options” (or groups). Other proposed taxonomies may follow
327 somewhat different terminology but overall similar patterns. Clearly, some customization
328 for racks is in order. Herein five basic attributes are chosen to characterize racking systems:
329 (i) structural typology, (ii) placement and cladding, (iii) height, (iv) storage system and (v)
330 design code level, as illustrated in Table 1 and discussed in detail in the following sections.

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342 Table 1. Proposed Rack taxonomy following the GEM breakdown to Attributes/Attribute-
343 Levels/Options

TaxT Attribute Group	#	Attribute	Attribute-Levels	Options	
				Description	ID
Structural System	1	Structural typology	Gravity Load-Resisting System	Uprights+beams Uprights+rails Cantilever	GUB GUR GC
			Down-aisle Lateral Load-Resisting System	Moment resisting frame Spine bracing Bracing tower	LMRF LSB LBT
			Steel type	Cold-formed Hot-rolled Mixed	CFS HRS MS
	2	Placement and cladding	Placement and cladding	Indoor racks Outdoor racks Clad-supporting racks	IDR ODR CLD
Rack Information	3	Height	Height	Low-rise [<8m] Medium-rise [8-12m] High-rise [12-20m] Very high-rise [>20m]	HL HM HH HVH
	4	Storage system	Unit load weight	Low [<200kg] Medium [200-1000kg] High [1000-2000kg]	WL WM WH
			Contact surface	Wood+Steel Plastic+Steel Steel+Steel Hanging goods	SURWS SURPS SURSS SURHG
			Material/goods handling	Manual Semi-automated Fully-automated	MA SA FA
	5	Design code level	Design code level	No-Code [Pre 1990 EU Pre 1976 USA] Mid-Code [1990-2008 EU 1976-1997 USA] High-Code [Post 2008 EU Post 1997 USA]	NC MC HC

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346 **4.1 Structural typology**

347 The first Attribute, the structural typology, defines the racking system as a civil engineering
348 structure that resists external loads and excitations. It is broken down to three Attribute-
349 Levels that describe the gravity and lateral load-resisting systems, and the type of steel used
350 for both. The Gravity Load-Resisting System (GLRS) Attribute-Level, self-evidently
351 describes the load path followed to transfer the gravity loads of the goods to the foundation.
352 Three different Options are proposed, namely “uprights+beams”, “uprights+rails”, and
353 “cantilever”. The majority of rack typologies belong to the “uprights+beams” group,
354 meaning that the goods are carried by pallet beams semi-rigidly connected to the uprights
355 (e.g. APR, pallet shuttle, ARSW, see Figure 14a). On the other hand, racks with no beams
356 along the down-aisle direction belong to the “uprights+rails” group (e.g. drive-in, drive-
357 through), where the goods are carried by continuous pallet rails that connect the individual
358 upright frames along the cross-aisle direction (Figure 14b). Finally, the “cantilever” Option
359 uses cantilever beams that are moment-connected to the uprights to accommodate the long
360 products (Figure 14c).

361

Figure 14: The GLRS Attribute-Level of the structural typology Attribute comprises three Options: (a) “uprights+beams”, (b) “uprights+rails” and (c) “cantilever”.

362

363 The second Attribute-Level is the Lateral Load-Resisting System (LLRS) in the down-aisle
364 direction, currently comprising the Options of MRF, spine bracing and bracing tower
365 (Figure 15). It can be extended in the future to contain more load-bearing systems (e.g. base
366 isolation (Simoncelli et al. 2020)) as they evolve. In the cross-aisle direction no distinction
367 was made, as the structural scheme always comprises upright frames, with the number of
368 connected frames being the only variable. The only potential exception is the cantilever
369 system, where the GLRS also fully describes the cross-aisle LLRS (which is simply that of
370 a cantilevered upright), thus no further delineation is needed. Further extending the
371 Attribute-Levels to consider the number of upright frames in the cross-aisle direction is a
372 possibility, as for example note that the American codes (RMI 2012) do consider the
373 positive effect of multiple upright frames connected (e.g. in the pallet shuttle or the drive-
374 in racks) by a so-called “redundancy factor”, assuming that a stress redistribution is possible
375 when the most critical structural member fails. However, research so far has demonstrated

376 that, especially in the cross-aisle direction, racks fail due to brittle failure modes and thus, a
377 local failure will probably initiate a sudden global collapse. Hence, in the interest of
378 simplicity, this further discretization of cross-aisle LLRS has not been introduced.

379 Finally, one may consider the type of steel used, which can be cold-formed, hot-rolled or
380 mixed, e.g. as in having the uprights of the bracing towers hot-rolled while the rest cold-
381 formed. The use of hot-rolled sections might imply a capacity design framework per
382 conventional building seismic design but this is the prerogative of the designer and not
383 necessitated by rack-specific guidelines. Thus, the distinction between cold-formed and hot-
384 rolled rack profiles does not necessarily imply an improved performance of the latter, but it
385 was considered for completeness.

386 Two potential Attribute-Levels of the structural typology Attribute, not considered herein
387 but may be added in the future, are related to the connection of the racking system with the
388 ground. The first potential Attribute-Level is the type of foundation, which can be concrete
389 slab, asphalt, tiles, suspended floors, etc. However, as the vast majority of racks are installed
390 on concrete slabs, the classification according to the type of foundation was disregarded for
391 reasons of simplicity. The second possible Attribute-Level is related to the behavior of the
392 base plates and the anchoring system. Indeed, the rotational stiffness and the hysteretic
393 behavior of the base plates can play a critical role on the seismic response of an unbraced
394 rack along the down-aisle direction (Bernuzzi and Simoncelli 2016b). They still comprise a
395 structural component of the LLRS Attribute-Level, just like the beam-to-column joints or
396 the spine braces. In this scope, as the APRs evolve to accommodate additional load levels
397 with heavier unit loads, one could divide the MRF Option to weak-MRF and strong-MRF,
398 indicating the use of flexible base plates and beam-to-column connections or not.

(c)
 Figure 15: The LLRS Attribute-Level of the structural typology Attribute comprises three Options: (a) MRF, (b) spine bracing and (c) bracing tower.

399

400 **4.2 Placement and Cladding**

401 Placement and cladding, the second Attribute of the proposed rack taxonomy, comprises
 402 three Options, the indoor, outdoor, and clad-supporting racks. In terms of applicable natural
 403 hazards, while indoor racks (Figure 16a) are designed only for seismic actions, the other
 404 two groups are also exposed to wind and snow hazards. Outdoor racks share many structural
 405 characteristics (dimensions, sections etc.) with indoor racks, however there is no external
 406 shell to protect them from the elements on all sides. Only a roof canopy may be installed at
 407 the top of the rack to partially shelter the stockpiled goods from rain and sun (Figure 16b).

408 Clad-supporting racks (i.e. the RSWs, Figure 16c) integrate the external envelope shell and
 409 the racking system into a compact structure. Typically, a shallow roof truss connects the
 410 upright frames in the cross-aisle direction, while horizontal bracing is employed to provide
 411 in-plane stiffness in the down-aisle direction. In general, the axially-stiff roof truss can be
 412 expected to enforce equal displacements at the topmost level of the uprights in the cross-
 413 aisle direction, but a fully rigid diaphragm is not necessarily realized due to the limited
 414 horizontal bracing. RSWs are especially vulnerable to wind during the erection phase, where
 415 the lateral load resisting system (typically bracing towers) has not been fully installed.

416

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 16: The placement and cladding Attribute comprises three Options: (a) indoor, (b) outdoor and (c) clad-supporting racks (photos courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

417 **4.3 Height**

418 The height of the racking system is adopted as the third Attribute. While for conventional
 419 buildings, the number of stories is often used as a proxy for height, the number of loading
 420 levels is not equally useful: The height of the load levels varies significantly among different
 421 warehouses, and even within the same structure, to serve different logistic demands.
 422 Conventionally, increased structural height is connected with augmented effects of higher
 423 modes, $P-\Delta$, and of course larger member sections. Specifically for racks, increased height
 424 also acts as a multiplier on the consequences of goods falling off due to lateral displacement
 425 of the rack, increasing the impact energy as well as the probability of landing on an adjacent
 426 rack, thus becoming a source of damage spreading and potential progressive collapse.

427

Figure 17: The height Attribute comprises four Options: (a) low-, (b) medium- (c) high- and (d) very high-rise racks (photos courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

428

429 Four Options were considered, which may not necessarily indicate a sharp difference in
 430 structural behavior, but certainly correspond to different levels of engineering requirements:
 431 low-rise racks (below 8 meters), medium-rise (8 to 12 meters), high-rise (12 to 20 meters)
 432 and finally very high-rise (above 20 meters), as illustrated in Figure 17. The low-rise
 433 threshold may be chosen to be lower, at 6 meters, where it would mainly comprise shelving
 434 racks and few APR and drive-in systems. By increasing the value to 8 meters, the low-rise
 435 group becomes the most populated among the four, as it includes a large percentage of APR
 436 systems world-wide. However, APR systems tend to increase in height to better exploit the
 437 available footprint and it will not be surprising if the medium-rise becomes the “typical”
 438 group in a few years.

439

440 **4.4 Storage system**

441 The fourth Attribute is related to the functionality of a rack, the so-called storage system. It
442 consists of three Attribute-Levels, namely the weight of the unit load, the contact surface
443 and the handling system.

444 Regarding the first Attribute-Level, one may consider the number of unit loads per
445 compartment instead of the weight of the unit load; but this can become ambiguous for the
446 case of multi-depth racking systems (e.g. a pallet shuttle racking system with 6 upright
447 frames and 14 pallet positions along the cross-aisle direction). Another rational choice
448 would have been adopting the average weight of goods per square meter of load level, but
449 racking technology seldomly uses this term, leading to ambiguity in subsequent discussions
450 with professionals, leaving unit load weight as the best and most familiar concept.

451 Three Options are proposed for the weight of the unit load: Low-weight (below 200 kg),
452 medium-weight (200 to 1000 kg) and high-weight (1000 to 2000 kg), as illustrated in Figure
453 18. Unit loads heavier than 2000 kg are seldomly used as they demand special analysis and
454 rack typology. The low-weight is the only Option related with hand-picking methods while
455 in the medium- and high-weight groups the goods are usually palletized and require
456 mechanical methods for their handling.

457

Figure 18: The weight of the unit load Attribute-Level of the storage system Attribute consists of three Options: (a) low-, (b) medium- and (c) high-weight (photos courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

458

459 Unit loads can be stored using pallets, containers, boxes, trays or even be hung, with the
460 pallets frequently related with heavier products. The engineering significance of such a
461 variety of different storing methods can be summarized in terms of the “contact surface”
462 between the goods and the rack as the second Attribute-Level. Goods may rest on top of
463 beams/rails, or hung from them. In both cases, the apparent inertia of the rack is typically
464 reduced during seismic excitations due to pendulum effects, for hanging goods, or sliding
465 of goods-on-steel. Still, in the latter case, a low friction constant may lead to displacements
466 of such magnitude that the products fall off and damage the adjacent racks, thus some
467 differentiation of the materials in contact is required.

468

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 19: The contact surface Attribute-Level of the storage system Attribute consists of four Options: (a) wood+steel, (b) plastic+steel, (c) steel+steel and (d) hanging goods (photos courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

469

470 Herein four Options are chosen, namely the “wood+steel”, “plastic+steel”, “steel+steel” and
471 the “hanging goods”, as illustrated in Figure 19. The majority of racking systems fall into
472 the “wood+steel” group, whereby wooden pallets are placed on steel beams. EN16681
473 (2016) gives high reference values of the friction constant for the “wood+steel” group
474 ($\mu=0.37$) and lower for the “plastic+steel” and “steel+steel” group ($\mu=0.15$). For the
475 “hanging goods” little experimental or analytical data is available, however the inertia forces
476 are relatively low in this kind of racking systems as they mainly store clothing products.
477 Finally, there are cases that do not fall into any of the four Options (i.e. the cheese units in
478 Figure 1b), but they are the exception, rather than the rule.

479

Figure 20: Material/goods handling Attribute-Level of the storage system Attribute consists of three Options: (a) manual, (b) semi-automated, and (c) fully-automated (photos courtesy of MECALUX S.A.).

480

481 The third Attribute-Level is related to the handling system of the goods, consisting of three
 482 Options (Figure 20): Manual (forklift trucks or hand-picking), semi-automated
 483 (shuttles+forklift trucks) and fully-automated (shuttles+cranes). In the fully-automated
 484 systems, such as the ARSWs, there is no need for human intervention in the handling
 485 process, which minimizes the risk for human losses during an earthquake. However, as the
 486 goods are now handled only via robotic means with specific tolerances, it is often the case
 487 that after an earthquake event the shuttles will not be able to target correctly the pallets, as
 488 they have been displaced. In fact, repositioning of the pallets within system tolerances is a
 489 labor-intensive process, as a special team of workers has to climb inside the warehouse and
 490 adjust the position of all the goods, a procedure that may take weeks, or even a month,
 491 leading to the complete shut-down of the warehouse.

493 **4.5 Design code level**

494 Probably the most critical Attribute for the seismic assessment of steel racks, and civil
495 engineering structures in general, is the design code level, which is closely correlated with
496 the date of construction or retrofit. One may choose to maintain both pieces of information
497 in the taxonomy as converting one to the other is not always straightforward. Herein, we
498 shall attempt to provide a mapping of age to the seismic code, at least in EU and USA.
499 Adding a separate “Date of construction or retrofit” Attribute can be easily done if needed
500 as in GEM 3.1 Building Taxonomy. In general, seismic vulnerability is expected to increase
501 with age, a universal trend that reflects the improvement of design and detailing standards
502 for practically all countries, as well as due to the general upwards trend of design spectra.
503 Specifically for racks, there are additional compounding reasons aggravating this
504 phenomenon. First is the lack of knowledge; in contrast to the residential steel buildings,
505 steel racks have only lately received the attention of the scientific community and
506 standardization bodies. This is reflected in the delayed appearance of specialized seismic
507 design codes for racks, in comparison to conventional buildings. For example, in USA, some
508 of the earliest seismic design requirements for racks appeared circa 1974 (see Chen et al.
509 (1980) for a detailed review), while for Europe the first draft of FEM 10.2.08 (2011) was
510 published in 2003 and introduced in practice in 2008. Secondly, seismic design was/is not
511 mandatory for racks in many countries, as they were/are considered as contents or
512 equipment rather than civil engineering structures. For racks designed before the
513 introduction of rack-specific codes, this led to a wide dispersion in the actually applied
514 design standards, from cases where only gravity loads were employed for the design, up to
515 some structures that received a full seismic design similar to conventional buildings. In fact,
516 there remain many countries today where non-seismic-resistant indoor/outdoor racks (but
517 not RSWs) may still be designed, and they are the standard go-to option to minimize the
518 cost of the storage facility. Still, awareness of the seismic issues is spreading, leading to
519 improved designs even where they are not mandated, especially in cases where the direct
520 cost of the stored goods or the indirect cost of service disruption is far greater than the cost
521 of the rack itself.

522 A comprehensive classification of racks according to their design code level is thus country-
523 specific and largely depends on local design/construction practices and the date of actual
524 code adoption, rather than the date of publication. Furthermore, most if not all guidelines
525 concern APR systems, leaving some wide space for interpretation regarding other rack
526 typologies. As an initial attempt, we propose classifying the racks into three groups with
527 indicative cut-off dates of 1990 & 2008 for Europe and 1976 & 1997 for USA. Those
528 constructed before the first cut-off date belong to the “no-code” group, meaning that the
529 vast majority was not designed for seismic loads. The second group structures, namely
530 “mid-code” racks, were built between the two cut-off dates (i.e. 1990–2008 for Europe and
531 1976–1997 for USA) using seismic design codes mostly meant for (or derived from)
532 conventional steel structures, such as EN 1998 (2004), UBC (1997), or other relevant
533 national codes. In general, for European racks this means that relatively high behavior

534 factors (e.g. 3.0 or greater) may have been employed, as recommended for conventional
535 steel buildings, but without necessarily accounting for capacity design to ensure a ductile
536 failure mechanism. For USA, the situation is more fragmented, as fairly conservative rules
537 were employed early on, which were later relaxed (Chen et al. 1980), while at the same time
538 subjected to changes in the design spectra. The third group comprises racks designed after
539 2008 for Europe, a milestone signifying the adoption of FEM 10.2.08 (2011) by EU
540 industry, and post 1997 for USA, thanks to the introduction of updated RMI (2012)
541 standards. Those "high-code" racks typically adopt low behavior factors, at least compared
542 to those of (superficially) similar conventional structures. For example, $q=1.5$ to 2.0 is
543 mandated for racks in EU (EN 16681 2016), compared to 4.0 for buildings with concentric-
544 braced frames and up to 6.5 for high-ductility moment-resisting frames per EN 1998-1
545 (2004). A direct comparison with USA practice is not necessarily informative due to other
546 differences in the design process, but RMI (2012) considers $R=4$ for braced directions of
547 racks and up $R=6$ for high-ductility unbraced ones, compared to $R=6$ for special concentric
548 braced frames and $R=8$ for special moment-resisting frames per ASCE7-16 (2017). Still, the
549 improvement in performance is only due to this increased overstrength, as connections and
550 members remain largely non-ductile.

551

552 **5 Available literature per proposed taxonomy**

553 To help populate and further substantiate the proposed taxonomy, we hereby classify several
554 analytical and experimental publications that focus on the response of racking systems
555 subjected to lateral loads according to the categorization of the racking structures studied.
556 As we are interested in the characterization of racks from a global point of view, studies that
557 investigated solely the behavior of individual components, like the beam-to-column joint,
558 were disregarded. The results appear in Table 2, showing the citation as well as the
559 Attribute-Levels of each studied structure. Only the "Design code level" property is
560 excluded, as design code is hard to determine for most case studies. In most cases, given the
561 post-2006 date of publication and the general focus on improving design, it can be safely
562 assumed that mid/high-code racks were studied.

563

Table 2: Publications related to the seismic performance of racks, categorized according to the proposed taxonomy

Authors	Rack typology	GLRS	Down-aisle LLRS	Steel type	Placement and Cladding	Height (m)	UL weight (kg)	Contact surface	Goods handling
Kondratenko et al. (2020)	ARSW	Uprights+Beams	Bracing Tower	Mixed	Clad-suppl.	VH ⁴ (22.0)	M (600-1000)	Wood+Steel	Fully-Autom.
Tsarpalis et al. (2021)	ARSW	Uprights+Beams	Bracing Tower	Mixed	Clad-suppl.	VH (22.0-30.0)	M (600-1000)	Wood+Steel	Fully-Autom.
Caprili et al. (2018)	ARSW	Uprights+Beams	Spine Bracing	Mixed	Clad-suppl.	VH (30.0)	M (1000)	Wood+Steel	Fully-Autom.
Franco et al. (2015)	Cantilever	Cantilever	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L ¹ (7.0)	L (40)	Other	Manual
Shaheen et al. (2019)	Drive-in	Uprights+Rails	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (4.9)	N/A	Wood+Steel	Manual
Gilbert et al. (2012)	Drive-in	Uprights+Rails	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (5.0)	H (1200-2000)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Gabbianelli et al. (2020)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (7.6)	M (295)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Bernuzzi et al. (2016b)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (8.0)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Gusella et al. (2018)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (8.0)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Filiatrault et al. (2006)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (4.5)	M (500)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Kanyilmaz et al. (2016)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	M ² (8.1-8.5)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Maguire et al. (2020)	APR	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (4.3)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Yin et al. (2018)	APR	Uprights+Beams	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	H ³ (19.8)	M (450)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Avgerinou et al. (2019)	APR	Uprights+Beams	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (7.9)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Kanyilmaz et al. (2016)	APR	Uprights+Beams	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (8.0)	M (800)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Gabbianelli et al. (2020)	APR	Uprights+Beams	Spine Bracing	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (7.6)	M (295)	Wood+Steel	Manual
Bernuzzi et al. (2016a)	Shelving	Uprights+Beams	MRF	Cold-formed	Indoor	L (2.0)	L-M (100-300)	Steel+Steel	Manual

¹L: Low, ²M: Medium, ³H: High, ⁴VH: Very-high

566 Clearly, the majority of case studies comprised cold-formed, low-rise, indoor racks carrying
567 medium-weight unit loads placed on pallets that are manually handled by forklift trucks; in
568 essence, the literature so far has focused on the low-rise APR systems. On the other hand, the
569 semi- and fully-automated systems, like the multi-depth pallet shuttle racks or the high-rise
570 ARSWs have not yet received enough academic attention, despite being very popular systems
571 in the market. Finally, only 2 out of 17 publications examined racks with bracing towers as the
572 down-aisle LLRS, showing a reliance on data available for similar building-style LLRS, but
573 potentially also a lack of knowledge for their idiosyncrasies when applied in the racking
574 industry.

575

576 **6 Conclusions**

577 A comprehensive review of the macro-characteristics of various racking typologies has been
578 conducted, focusing on their structural behavior under lateral loading conditions. It follows the
579 same terminology as the Building Taxonomy developed by the Global Earthquake Model,
580 comprising five basic “Attributes” required to broadly characterize any racking system: (i)
581 structural typology, (ii) placement and cladding, (iii) height, (iv) storage system and (v) design
582 code level. Each “Attribute” is broken down to several “Attribute Levels” delineating, e.g., the
583 different types of lateral load-resisting systems or handling methods, and then further
584 discretized to several “Options” (or groups).

585 In general, the vast majority of racks tend to conform to the low-rise APR type thus, for
586 frugality, the taxonomy may be collapsed to examining archetypes of this type for no/mid/high
587 code groups.

588 Although the taxonomy is mainly developed for seismic conditions, it is general enough that it
589 can also be adopted or modified for wind loads or other extreme hazards.

590 It is designed to be extensible, meaning that it can easily accommodate new rack typologies
591 and load-bearing mechanisms without changing the proposed five basic Attributes.

592 It is user-friendly and intuitive, as the considered macro-characteristics can easily be identified
593 by a non-expert, just by looking at pictures of the racking system.

594

595 **Declarations**

596 **1. Funding**

597 The first author acknowledges the financial support provided by Greece and the European
598 Union (European Social Fund – ESF) through the Operational Programme «Human Resources
599 Development, Education and Lifelong Learning» in the context of the project “Strengthening
600 Human Resources Research Potential via Doctorate Research” (MIS-5000432), implemented
601 by the State Scholarships Foundation (IKY). Additional funding was provided by the European
602 Commission through the Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) Project STEELWAR,
603 under Grant Agreement Number 754102.

604

605 **2. Conflicts of interest/Competing interests**

606 Not applicable.

607 **3. Availability of data and material**

608 Some or all data, models or code that support the findings of this study are available from the
609 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

610

611 **4. Code availability**

612 Not applicable.

613

614 **5. Ethics approval**

615 Not applicable.

616

617 **6. Consent to participate**

618 Not applicable.

619

620 **7. Consent for publication**

621 Not applicable.

622

623 **Acknowledgements**

624 The help of Dr. Ettore Fagà on issues of taxonomy is gratefully acknowledged. The authors
625 also thank Dr. Vitor Silva for his thoughtful comments and efforts towards improving this
626 manuscript.

627

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